

All the P and K and half the N were applied as basal before transplanting. Rice cultivar Sarjoo 52 was transplanted 18 Jul 1985. Pyrite was topdressed but not incorporated 20 d after transplanting. The remaining N was topdressed at tillering and panicle

initiation.

Each fertilizer level increased grain yield significantly. Increasing pyrite levels showed a linear yield response at all fertilizer levels except the low level. There was no interaction between pyrite rate and fertilizer rate.

Several aspects of pyrite application-application time, long-term application on normal soils, and causes of yield increases-are being studied. □

Effect of source and level of phosphorus on rice - grass pea (*Lathyrus sativus*)

N. R. Das and A. Sarkar, Agronomy Department, Faculty of Agriculture, Bidhan Chandra Krishi Viswavidyalaya, Kalyani 741235, West Bengal, India

We evaluated the effect of P level on yield of rainfed lowland rice - grass pea cropping sequence in 1988-89. P sources were single superphosphate, ammonium polyphosphate liquid 16:32% NP, and IFFCO-complex. The 5.0- × 2.5-m plots were laid out in a split-plot design with four replications.

Soil was clayey loam with 0.60% organic C, 0.06% total N, 17 kg available P and 187 kg available K/ha, and pH 6.8. IR36 was transplanted 17

Jul, 22 d after seeding, at 25- × 25-cm spacing, with four seedlings/hill. Fertilizer was broadcast at transplanting. N and K in P sources were calculated and urea and potassium chloride used to total 50-25 NK/ha.

One day before rice harvest on 30 Oct, grass pea cultivar Nirmal seeds (25 kg/ha) were broadcast uniformly over the rice crop. Immediately after rice harvest, half the plot was covered with 1.0 t/ha rice straw mulch. Grass pea was harvested 27 Feb 1989.

Rice grain yield did not differ with P source (see table). Grass pea grain yield was best with residual P from single superphosphate.

Rice straw mulch on grass pea after rainfed lowland rice was superior to no-mulch for both grass pea grain and straw yields. □

Effect of source and level of P on grain and straw yields of rice and grass pea. Kalyani, West Bengal, India, 1988-89.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)			
	Rice		Grass pea	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
<i>Source of P</i>				
Single super-phosphate	4.5	4.6	2.2	2.5
Ammonium poly-phosphate	3.8	3.8	2.0	2.0
IFFCO-complex	4.1	4.3	1.8	2.0
LSD (0.05)	ns	0.7	0.1	0.2
<i>Level of P (kg/ha)</i>				
4.4	3.5	3.7	1.8	1.9
8.8	4.3	4.8	2.1	2.2
13.2	4.6	4.1	2.1	2.3
LSD (0.05)	0.7	0.7	0.1	0.2
<i>Rice straw mulch (t/ha)</i>				
0.0	-	-	1.4	1.3
1.0	-	-	2.6	3.0
LSD (0.05)	-	-	0.1	0.1

Fertilizer management—organic sources

Nitrogen equivalence of green manure for wetland rice on coarse-textured soils

Y. Singh, B. Singh, O. P. Meelu, and M. S. Maskina, Soils Department, Punjab Agricultural University, Ludhiana 141004, India

We studied the relative effect of green manure N and inorganic N on rice grain yield in field experiments in 1986-88. Soil was loamy sand to sandy loam with pH 7.4 to 8.2, 0.30-0.40% organic C, and 0.06-0.08% total N.

Green manure crops *Sesbania aculeata*, sunn hemp *Crotalaria juncea*, and cowpea *Vigna unguiculata* were sown the first week of May and incorporated at 50 to 60 d old 1 d before transplanting rice. Total biomass and N in the green manure crops were determined at incorporation.

In plots without green manure, four levels of urea (0 to 180 kg N/ha) were applied in equal splits at 7, 21, and 42 d after transplanting. Basal 13-25 kg PK/ha was applied at transplanting.

Rice grain yield with urea alone increased significantly up to 180 kg N/ha. The grain yield data were fitted to quadratic response functions and the fertilizer N equivalence of green manure N computed (the amount of

inorganic N required to produce yields similar to those obtained with green manure alone).

Green manure added 41-150 kg N/ha depending on the source. In general, green manure N was equal to or better than urea N in increasing grain yield of rice (see table). The N equivalence was 35% higher than urea N and for cowpea, 20% for sunn hemp, and 15% for sesbania. □

Inorganic N equivalence of green manure in wetland rice. Ludhiana, India, 1986-88.

Green manure	Experiments (no.)	Green manure N added (kg/ha)	Rice yield (t/ha)		Inorganic N equivalence (kg/ha)
			No green manure	Green manure	
Sesbania	5	45- 75	3.3	5.0	72
	11	97-150	3.6	6.3	136
Sunn hemp	3	41- 70	3.1	4.5	72
	2	101-140	3.5	7.1	148
Cowpea	4	55 - 80	3.1	5.5	98